

Nanoscale thermal transport and entropy generation in magnetized MgO-Ag/water Williamson hybrid nanofluid over a shrinking surface

Gopinath Mandal^{1*}, Dulal Pal²

¹*Siksha-Satra, Visva-Bharati (An Institution of National Importance), Sriniketan, India, Pin 731 236.*

²*Department of Mathematics, Visva-Bharati (An Institution of National Importance), Santiniketan, West Bengal, India, Pin 731 235.*

Abstract

This research focuses on steady, laminar, and incompressible non-Newtonian magnetohydrodynamic flow of a Williamson hybrid nanofluid comprising magnesium oxide (MgO) and silver (Ag) nanoparticles suspended in water over a shrinking sheet. This study also investigate the importance of stability analysis in identifying dual solutions and evaluating heat transfer performance in hybrid nanofluids subjected to viscous dissipation and convective boundary conditions employing an artificial neural network (ANN). A mathematical framework is developed using nondimensional transformations and solved numerically via MATLAB's BVP4C routine to uncover dual solution behavior and analyze the role of key dimensionless parameters in fluid motion and heat transport. The investigation assesses the effects of various parameters on velocity, temperature, Nusselt number, skin friction coefficient, and entropy generation profiles. Dual solutions are observed for shrinking parameter λ up to a critical threshold λ_c , especially under strong suction conditions (S). Stability is examined through the computation of the smallest eigenvalue (β), revealing that the primary solution is stable, whereas the secondary one is unstable. Findings indicate that increasing nanoparticle concentration and the Weissenberg number leads to greater frictional resistance. Furthermore, entropy production rises significantly with changes in nanoparticle volume fraction and Weissenberg number, with hybrid nanofluids showing more pronounced effects than normal nanofluid or base fluid. The ANN model proves to be highly reliable, yielding error levels between 10^{-7} and 10^{-9} and regression coefficients nearing unity, which highlights the model's predictive strength. These insights contribute to advancing thermal management strategies in engineering applications, particularly those requiring efficient cooling mechanisms.

Key words: Williamson hybrid nanofluid; Magnetic field; Convective boundary condition; Stability analysis; Entropy generation; Artificial neural network (ANN).

* *Author's E-mail:* gopi_math1985@rediffmail.com; contact: 9432835393

Nomenclature

Br	Brinkman number
Bi	Biot number
B_0	Magnetic field strength
C_p	Specific heat at constant pressure, ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$(\rho C_p)_{nf}$	Nanofluid heat capacitance, ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
$(\rho C_p)_{hnf}$	Hybrid nanofluid heat capacitance, ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
C_f	Local skin-friction coefficient
Ec	Eckert number
E_g	Entropy generation (J/K)
$F(\eta)$	Dimensionless velocity
h_f	Heat transfer coefficient
M	Magnetic field parameter
Nu_x	Local Nusselt number
N_s	Dimensionless entropy generation
Pr	Prandtl number, $Pr = \mu c_p / \kappa$
q_w	Heat flux at the wall
Re_x	Local Reynolds number, $Re_x = U_w x / \nu$
S	Suction parameter
$T_w(x)$	Surface temperature of the sheet (K)
T	Nanofluid temperature (K)
T_∞	Free-stream temperature (K)
$u_w(x)$	Velocity of the shrinking/stretching sheet (m/s)
u, v	Velocity components in x and y directions (m/s)
We	Weissenberg number
x, y	Cartesian coordinates along and normal to the surface

Greek letters

τ	dimensionless time variable
Γ	time constant
τ_0	extra stress tensor
μ_0	shear stress
Λ_1	Rivlin-Ericksen tensor
ϕ_1	<i>MgO</i> nanoparticles's solid volume fraction
ϕ_2	<i>Ag</i> nanoparticles's solid volume fraction
ϕ_{hnf}	nanoparticles's solid volume fraction of hybrid nanofluid
η	similarity variable
κ_f	thermal conductivity of fluid ($Wm^{-1}K$)
κ_{nf}	mono nanofluid's thermal conductivity ($Wm^{-1}K$)
κ_{hnf}	hybrid nanofluid's thermal conductivity ($Wm^{-1}K$)
κ_s	nanoparticle's thermal conductivity($Wm^{-1}K$)
μ_f	fluid dynamic viscosity ($kg\ m^{-1}s^{-1}$)
μ_{nf}	mono nanofluid' effective viscosity($kg\ m^{-1}s^{-1}$)
μ_{hnf}	hybrid nanofluid's effective viscosity($kg\ m^{-1}s^{-1}$)
ν_f	fluid kinematic viscosity, μ_f/ρ_f (m^2s^{-1})
ρ_f	fluid density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
ρ_{nf}	mono nanofluid's effective density($kg\ m^{-3}$)
ρ_{hnf}	hybrid nanofluid's effective density of ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
ρ_s	density of nanoparticles ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
λ	shrinking parameter
σ	Electrical conductivity of the fluid (Ω/m)
σ_{nf}	Electrical conductivity of mono nanofluid (Ω/m)
σ_{hnf}	Electrical conductivity of hybrid nanofluid (Ω/m)
θ	Dimensionless temperature
ψ	Stream function

Subscripts

f	Fluid fraction
nf	Mono nanofluid
hnf	Hybrid nanofluid
s_1	Solid fraction of <i>MgO</i> nanoparticles
s_2	Solid fraction of <i>Ag</i> nanoparticles

Abbreviations

<i>ODE</i>	Ordinary Differential Equation
<i>PDE</i>	Partial Differential Equation
<i>HNF</i>	Hybrid Nanofluid
<i>NF</i>	Nanofluid
<i>RF</i>	Regular Fluid

1 Introduction

In recent decades, researchers across various disciplines have made significant strides in developing advanced energy transfer fluids, with applications extending to engineering and industrial applications. Despite this progress, a comprehensive understanding of the behavior, transport properties, and real-world applicability of nanofluids remains an ongoing research challenge. Nanofluids exhibit unique thermal and physical properties, making them valuable in diverse sectors including pharmaceuticals, biomedical engineering, electronics, household appliances (e.g., refrigerators), and systems used in power and chemical engineering. To further enhance heat transfer efficiency, a newer category known as hybrid nanofluids has emerged. Unlike traditional nanofluids that are formulated with a single type of nanoparticle, hybrid nanofluids combine two or more types of nanoparticles within a base fluid, offering improved thermal characteristics [1]. According to Sajjad et al. [2], hybrid nanofluids show great promise in various thermal management systems such as heat exchangers, compact channel radiators, and thermal conduits. Devi and Devi [3] examined heat transfer performance on two-dimensional stretching surfaces using a hybrid nanofluid composed of aluminium oxide and copper nanoparticles. Their findings revealed a significant enhancement in heat transfer rates compared to standard nanofluids. Similarly, Hayat et al. [4] studied the heat transfer characteristics of a silver–copper oxide/water hybrid nanofluid and observed improved thermal performance. Jamshed et al. [5] also reported higher

thermal exponents for hybrid nanofluids relative to conventional ones when suspending two different nanoparticles in a base fluid. Additionally, Sreedevi et al. [6] analyzed unsteady hybrid nanofluid flow—comprising carbon nanotubes and silver nanoparticles—over a stretching sheet with the influence of thermal radiation. In recent years, growing research efforts [7–11] have focused on enhancing the thermal conductivity of conventional nanofluids through the use of these innovative hybrid nanofluid formulations.

Pseudo-plastic fluids, a subclass of non-Newtonian fluids, are widely utilized in various engineering and industrial applications. These include photographic emulsions, high molecular weight polymer solutions and melts, blood and plasma flow, suspensions, sheet extrusion, and lubrication systems involving greases and heavy oils. To capture the complex rheological behavior of such fluids, several mathematical models have been proposed, including the Carreau, Ellis, Jeffery, Cross, power-law, Powell–Eyring, Sisko, and Williamson models. The Williamson model, first introduced by Williamson in 1929 [12], was specifically developed to describe the flow behavior of pseudo-plastic materials. A distinguishing feature of this model is its incorporation of both maximum and minimum effective viscosities, reflecting the fluid’s molecular structure. Unlike other models where viscosity tends to zero at high shear rates, the Williamson model ensures a finite lower limit, yielding more physically accurate predictions for certain applications. In recent studies, the Williamson fluid model has been extended to hybrid and nanofluid contexts. Kulkarni et al. [13] explored mixed convective flow of a Williamson nanofluid over a stretching/shrinking wedge, incorporating the effects of chemical reactions. Abbas et al. [14] analyzed a similar fluid flow with nonlinear thermal radiation over an exponentially stretching/shrinking surface. Rehman et al. [15] examined the behavior of a couple stress Williamson nanofluid including slip effects and viscous dissipation near a shrinking sheet. Saini et al. [16] addressed unsteady MHD Darcy–Forchheimer flow of a Williamson nanofluid, highlighting the emergence of dual solutions in the presence of chemical reactions and viscous dissipation, along with a stability analysis to determine the nature of these solutions. Gomathi et al. [17] also reported dual solutions for Casson–Williamson nanofluid flow influenced by thermal radiation and chemical reactions over a shrinking surface. More recently, Jamrus et al. [18] investigated the stability of non-Newtonian ternary hybrid nanofluid flows—modeled using the Williamson framework—over a stretching/shrinking sheet. Furthermore, Mandal and Pal [19] conducted an analysis of entropy generation in Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow, considering a magnetic field and nonlinear thermal radiation within a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium.

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) is an interdisciplinary field that explores the behavior of electrically conducting fluids in the presence of magnetic fields, merging principles from both fluid dynamics and electromagnetism. When such fluids move through a magnetic field, electric currents are induced, which, in turn, can influence both the fluid’s motion and its thermal characteristics. The foundational work in this area was introduced by Hartmann [20],

who investigated the laminar flow of an electrically conductive fluid within a uniform magnetic field, laying the groundwork for modern MHD studies. Numerous researchers have since extended the application of MHD principles to complex fluids, such as nanofluids and hybrid nanofluids. Bhatti et al. [21] examined the MHD flow of a Williamson nanofluid containing gyrotactic microorganisms through a porous medium. Nasir et al. [22] investigated the effect of an induced magnetic field on stagnation-point flow and heat transfer of an Ag–MgO/water hybrid nanofluid over a moving surface. Alkasasbeh et al. [23] analyzed how a magnetic field impacts the flow of a Williamson hybrid nanofluid past an exponentially shrinking sheet embedded in a porous medium. Maiti and Nandy [24] further explored the influence of magnetic fields on unsteady flow and heat transfer behavior of Williamson nanofluids over permeable shrinking surfaces. Jakeer and Reddy [25] focused on entropy generation in the electro-magnetohydrodynamic stagnation-point flow of a silver–copper/water hybrid nanofluid over a permeable, stretching/shrinking slender sheet. In addition, Sakkaravarthi and Reddy [26] investigated entropy generation in the MHD flow of a Williamson hybrid nanofluid over a permeable, curved, stretching/shrinking surface, considering the influence of multiple forms of thermal radiation. In essence, the magnetic field acts as a tool to fine-tune the properties of hybrid nanofluids, making them more versatile and efficient for a wide range of applications [27-29].

A shrinking sheet refers to a surface that contracts toward a fixed point—typically the origin—resulting in a decreasing surface area over time. When nanofluids are introduced to flow over such a sheet, their enhanced thermal conductivity significantly alters the boundary layer properties and heat transfer characteristics compared to those of conventional fluids. The application of nanofluid flow over shrinking surfaces holds considerable potential in advanced material processing and thermal management systems. Specific uses include controlling the thickness or alignment of materials, acting as lubricants or coolants to minimize thermal stress, preventing defects like warping or uneven cooling, improving thermal regulation in rolling mill operations, and even supporting biomedical procedures such as targeted drug delivery or nanofluid-based cryotherapy. Additionally, incorporating nanoparticles into lubricants can reduce friction and improve heat dissipation. Roy and Pop [30] demonstrated the existence of dual solutions for nanofluid flow over a convectively heated, nonlinearly shrinking sheet. Khashi'ie et al. [31] similarly reported multiple solutions in the context of MHD radiative three-dimensional bidirectional nanofluid flow across a nonlinearly permeable shrinking sheet. Abu Bakar et al. [32] investigated hybrid nanofluid flow past a permeable, melting shrinking sheet, incorporating higher-order slip conditions, shape factors, and viscous dissipation. Lund conducted a stability analysis to examine the presence of multiple solutions for hybrid nanofluid flow over stretching/shrinking surfaces. More recently, Kaswan et al. [33] analyzed nonlinear radiative magnetohydrodynamic flow of an $Ag - TiO_2$ /water hybrid nanofluid over a nonlinearly shrinking sheet, revealing dual solutions and conducting stability analysis to determine their

viability. Khan et al. [34] studied magnetized Williamson nanofluid flow across a stretching/shrinking sheet under the influence of velocity and thermal slip conditions.

In engineering applications, solving heat transfer problems increasingly relies on computational intelligence. Artificial intelligence, particularly artificial neural networks (ANNs), has emerged as a powerful approach that mimics human cognitive processes to model complex systems. ANNs utilize empirical or simulation data to derive correlations, minimize mean square error, and make predictions even without a full understanding of the physical laws governing the system. These networks, inspired by the human brain's neural architecture, are composed of layers of interconnected nodes (neurons) that process and relate inputs to outputs. Due to their flexibility and accuracy, ANNs have been applied in diverse heat transfer applications—such as optimizing steam generation systems, modeling airflow in ventilated enclosures, reclaiming heat from exchangers, and evaluating thermal system performance. Ziaei-Rad et al. [35] employed an ANN model to simulate and predict MHD nanofluid flow with dissipation effects over a permeable stretching surface. Haq et al. [36] recently used ANN techniques to validate numerical results for MHD nanofluid flow past a curved stretching sheet. Raja et al. [37] developed an ANN-based model aligned with the Buongiorno nanofluid theory for flow over a stretching surface. Tanuja [38] used ANN methods to estimate thermal conductivity in porous rectangular fins containing ternary hybrid nanofluids. Alimi et al. [39] applied ANNs to analyze heat transfer behavior of a water-based hybrid nanofluid flowing over a permeable stretching surface under the influence of an inclined magnetic field and thermal radiation. Furthermore, Naveen et al. [40] utilized ANN modeling to compute entropy generation in Casson hybrid nanofluid flow scenarios.

In recent years, hybrid nanofluids have attracted considerable attention due to their superior thermophysical properties, positioning them as promising materials for use in advanced thermal management systems and various industrial applications. A particularly effective combination involves dispersing magnesium oxide (MgO) and silver (Ag) nanoparticles in a water (H_2O) base fluid, which has demonstrated potential for enhancing heat transfer efficiency. Moreover, the inclusion of non-Newtonian characteristics, such as those exhibited by Williamson fluids, adds complexity to the flow behavior through shear-thinning effects, influencing both fluid motion and thermal performance. The numerical analysis of heat transfer and viscous dissipation in Williamson hybrid nanofluid (HNF) flow over a stretching surface has far-reaching relevance in fields like energy systems, industrial manufacturing, and electronic cooling technologies.

1.1 Novelty of the work

The proposed research includes several unique contributions, which are outlined as follows:

- (1) This research extends the Williamson fluid model—characterized by non-Newtonian, shear-thinning, and elastic properties—to the context of shrinking surface geometries, which has not been extensively explored in prior studies.
- (2) It investigates the behavior of hybrid nanofluids formed by dispersing magnesium oxide (MgO) and silver (Ag) nanoparticles in a water-based fluid, combined with the rheological complexity of Williamson fluid.
- (3) The model incorporates the combined effects of viscous dissipation, an externally applied magnetic field, and convective boundary conditions, which collectively enhance flow stability and heat transfer efficiency.
- (4) The existence of multiple (dual) solutions under certain parameter regimes is demonstrated using MATLAB's BVP4C solver. A subsequent stability analysis distinguishes the physically reliable solution, offering critical insights for the design and optimization of thermal systems.
- (5) A novel application of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) with the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm (LMA) is proposed to intelligently model and interpret heat transfer performance in wire-coating processes using hybrid nanofluids across varied conditions.
- (6) The study emphasizes entropy optimization to maintain uniform material flow—crucial for achieving high-quality surface finishes and structural integrity. By addressing challenges such as excessive thermal buildup and elevated friction, this work enhances product reliability and operational lifespan, with practical implications for sectors like electronics, energy systems, manufacturing, biomedical applications, environmental engineering, and the aerospace and automotive industries.

1.2 Objectives

This study has the following objectives:

- (1) Develop a comprehensive theoretical framework to model and analyze the heat transfer and flow characteristics of a Williamson hybrid nanofluid

(*MgO – Ag/water*) flowing over a shrinking sheet geometry.

- (2) Investigate the influence of Williamson fluid parameters on the flow dynamics and thermal behavior of the hybrid nanofluid under varying nanoparticle concentration levels. Additionally, assess the effects of magnetic field intensity and Eckert number on key flow and heat transfer characteristics.
- (3) Conduct a comparative analysis of the heat transfer performance of hybrid nanofluids against that of conventional nanofluids (single-type nanoparticles) and the pure base fluid, highlighting the improvements in thermal efficiency.
- (4) Validate the numerical results obtained through the proposed BVP4C-based scheme by comparing them with predictions from an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model, emphasizing accuracy and consistency across both approaches.

2 Formulation of the Problem

A detailed description of the Williamson fluid model is available in [41]

$$S = -PI + \tau_0, \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_0 = \left[\mu_\infty + \frac{\mu_0 - \mu_\infty}{1 - \Gamma\dot{\gamma}} \right] \Lambda_1, \quad (2)$$

Here Λ_1 is first Rivlin-Ericksen tensor, S is Cauchy stress tensor, μ_∞ is the infinite shear stress, μ_0 is zero shear stress, τ_0 is the extra stress tensor, Γ is the time constant, $\dot{\gamma}$ is defined as,

$$\dot{\gamma} = \sqrt{\frac{\Pi}{2}}, \quad \Pi = \text{Trace}(\Lambda_1^2) = 2 \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right]^2, \quad (3)$$

Consider the case μ_0 , the τ_0 can be written as:

$$\tau_0 = \left[\frac{\mu_0}{1 - \Gamma\dot{\gamma}} \right] \Lambda_1, \quad (4)$$

After expansion of this we have this results

$$\tau_0 = \left[\mu_0 + (1 + \Gamma\dot{\gamma}) \right] \Lambda_1, \quad (5)$$

In this study, we analyze a steady, incompressible, and viscous, and chemically reactive Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow influenced by magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) effects, induced by a shrinking sheet moving with velocity

$u_w = ax$ (xy -plane). A uniform transverse magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = (0, B_0, 0)$ is imposed, assuming the absence of magnetic induction. The velocity component normal to the sheet, denoted by $v_w(x)$, represents the suction or injection velocity at the surface. It is assumed that the nanoparticles suspended in the base fluid remain in thermal equilibrium. Based on these assumptions, the governing equations for heat and mass transfer within the flow are expressed as follows (see [42]–[43]):

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \sqrt{2}\Gamma \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\sigma_{hnf} B_0^2}{\rho_{hnf}} u, \quad (7)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}} \frac{d^2 T}{dy^2} + \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^3 \right], \quad (8)$$

The appropriate convective boundary conditions are ([44]–[46])

$$u = u_w, \quad v = v_w, \quad -\kappa_{hnf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h_f(T - T_w), \quad \text{at } y = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$u \rightarrow U_\infty = 0, \quad v \rightarrow 0, \quad T \rightarrow T_\infty, \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty, \quad (10)$$

where h_f represents the ratio of heat exchange, and T_∞ specify the ambient temperature. The hybrid nanofluid's density ρ_{hnf} , heat capacitance $(\rho C_p)_{hnf}$, dynamic viscosity μ_{hnf} , electrical conductivity σ_{hnf} , thermal conductivity κ_{hnf} , employed in Eqs. (6)–(10) are characterized in Table-1

Table 1

Thermophysical properties of nanofluid and hybrid nanofluid (Mandal and Pal [19])

Properties	Nanofluid and Hybrid Nanofluid		
Density	$\frac{\rho_{nf}}{\rho_f} = (1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f}, \quad \frac{\rho_{hnf}}{\rho_f} = (1 - \phi_2)[(1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f}] + \phi_2 \frac{\rho_{s2}}{\rho_f}$		
Dynamic viscosity	$\frac{\mu_{nf}}{\mu_f} = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5}}, \quad \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}, \quad \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} = \frac{1}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5}(1 - \phi_2)^{2.5}}$		
Heat Capacitance	$\frac{(\rho C_p)_{nf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} = (1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s1}}{(\rho C_p)_f}, \quad \frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} = (1 - \phi_2) + \phi_2 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s2}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}},$ $\frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} = (1 - \phi_2)[(1 - \phi_1) + \phi_1 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s1}}{(\rho C_p)_f}] + \phi_2 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s2}}{(\rho C_p)_f}$		
Electrical conductivity	$\frac{\sigma_{nf}}{\sigma_f} = 1 - \frac{3\phi_1[1 - \frac{\sigma_{s1}}{\sigma_f}]}{[2 + \frac{\sigma_{s1}}{\sigma_f}] + \phi_1[1 - \frac{\sigma_{s1}}{\sigma_f}]}, \quad \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_{nf}} = 1 - \frac{3\phi_2[1 - \frac{\sigma_{s2}}{\sigma_{nf}}]}{[2 + \frac{\sigma_{s2}}{\sigma_{nf}}] + \phi_2[1 - \frac{\sigma_{s2}}{\sigma_{nf}}]}, \quad \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_f} = \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_{nf}} \times \frac{\sigma_{nf}}{\sigma_f}$		
Thermal conductivity	$\frac{\kappa_{nf}}{\kappa_f} = \frac{\kappa_{s1} + 2\kappa_f - 2\phi_1(\kappa_f - \kappa_{s1})}{\kappa_{s1} + 2\kappa_f + \phi_1(\kappa_f - \kappa_{s1})}, \quad \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_{nf}} = \frac{\kappa_{s2} + 2\kappa_{nf} - 2\phi_2(\kappa_{nf} - \kappa_{s2})}{\kappa_{s2} + 2\kappa_{nf} + \phi_2(\kappa_{nf} - \kappa_{s2})}, \quad \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} = \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_{nf}} \times \frac{\kappa_{nf}}{\kappa_f}$		

2.1 Similarity transformation

The boundary value problem (BVP) described by the governing equations is transformed into a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) through

the application of similarity transformations and the introduction of a stream function (ψ), as follows:

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}}y, \quad \psi = \sqrt{c\nu_f}xF(\eta), \quad u = cxF'(\eta),$$

$$v = -\sqrt{c\nu_f}F'(\eta), \quad \theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}. \quad (11)$$

Reduced ordinary differential equations by making use of similarity transformations are:

$$\frac{\mu_{hnf}/\mu_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f}F'''' + WeF''F'''' + FF'' - F'^2 - \frac{\sigma_{hnf}/\sigma_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f}MF' = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \theta'' + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} F \theta' + \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} \left(1 + \frac{We}{2} F''\right) Ec F''^2 = 0, \quad (13)$$

with reduced boundary conditions:

$$F(\eta) = S, \quad F'(\eta) = \lambda, \quad \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \theta'(\eta) = -Bi(1 - \theta(\eta)), \quad \eta = 0, \quad (14)$$

$$F'(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (15)$$

Key physical quantities of interest in engineering and manufacturing include Table 2
The emerging physical parameters

Parameter values	Notation	Parameter Name	Parameter range
$(\lambda = \frac{a}{c})$	(λ)	Shrinking parameter	$-3.0 \leq \lambda \leq -1.0$
$(M = \frac{\sigma B_0^2}{c\rho_f})$	(M)	Magnetic field parameter	$0.0 \leq M \leq 0.1$
$(We = x\sqrt{2}\Gamma \frac{c^{3/2}}{\nu_f^{1/2}})$	(We)	Weissenberg number	$0.01 \leq We \leq 0.3$
$(Pr = \frac{\nu_f(\rho C_p)_f}{\kappa_f})$	(Pr)	Prandtl number	$Pr = 6.8$
$(Ec = \frac{c^2}{bC_{pf}})$	(Ec)	Eckert number	$0.01 \leq Ec \leq 0.2$
$(S = -\frac{v_w}{\sqrt{c\nu_f}})$	(S)	Wall mass flux transfer parameter	$2.5 \leq S \leq 3.5$
$(Bi = \frac{h_f}{\kappa_f} \sqrt{\frac{\nu_f}{c}})$	(Bi)	Biot number	$0.1 \leq Bi \leq 5.0$

the velocity gradient (shear stress) normal to the surface, the temperature gradient specified at the wall of shrinking sheet (see Mandal and Pal [16]) is

$$C_f = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_f u_w^2} \left\{ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\Gamma}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\}_{y=0}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{\kappa_{hnf} \left(-\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}}{\kappa_f (T_w - T_\infty)/x}, \quad (16)$$

Using (11) in (16), the dimensionless form of physical quantities, i.e., skin-friction coefficient, Nusselt number, and local Sherwood number, can be expressed as

$$Re_x^{1/2}C_f = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f}(F''(0) + WeF'''(0)^2), \quad Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x = -\frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f}\theta'(0), \quad (17)$$

where $Re_x = u_w(x)x/\nu_f$ is the local Reynolds number based on the stretching velocity $u_w(x)$.

Table 3

Thermophysical aspects of the nanoparticles and base fluid (Dharmaiah et al. [8])

<i>Nanoparticles</i>				
Properties	Water(H_2O)	Ag	MgO	Unit
ρ	997.1	10500	3560	$J/kg K$
C_p	4179	233	955	kg/m^3
κ	0.613	429	45	$W/m K$
σ	5.5×10^{-6}	63×10^6	5.392×10^{-7}	Ω/m
Pr	6.8	--	--	--

Table 4

Comparison of $f''(0)$ and $-\theta'(0)$ for viscous fluid ($\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = 0$) when $S = 3$, $Pr = 0.7$ and $M = Nr = Gr = Fr = A = C = 0$ for the shrinking sheet ($\xi = -1$).

	$f''(0)$		$-\theta'(0)$	
	$1^{st} sol$	$2^{nd} sol$	$1^{st} sol$	$2^{nd} sol$
Ghosh & Mukhopadhyay [47]	2.39082	-0.97223	1.7712	0.84832
Waini et al. [48]	2.390814	-0.972247	1.771237	0.848316
Prsent Results	2.3908136	-0.9721280	1.7712383	0.8478486

2.2 Entropy generation

Entropy generation, often referred to as second law analysis, serves as a vital tool for quantifying energy loss and degradation in the performance of engineering and industrial systems, including various rate and transport processes.

Table 5
Scenario, case studies and emerging parameters.

Scenario (S_n)	Case(C)	Parameters							
		λ	S	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	We	M	Ec	Bi
S_1	1	-0.5	2.5	0.01	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.1
	2	-1.0	2.8	0.05	0.05	0.2	0.05	0.05	0.2
	3	-2.0	3.0	0.10	0.1	0.4	0.10	0.10	0.5
S_2	1	-0.5	2.5	0.01	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.1
	2	-1.0	2.8	0.05	0.05	0.2	0.05	0.05	0.2
	3	-2.0	3.0	0.10	0.1	0.4	0.10	0.10	0.5

Table 6
Results of ANN for two different cases and scenarios.

Scenario (S_n)	Case(C)	Performance	Mu	Gradient	Epochs
S_1	1	$5.77E - 09$	$1.00E - 09$	$9.68E - 08$	213
	2	$1.27E - 09$	$1.00E - 11$	$9.64E - 08$	290
	3	$2.80E - 09$	$1.00E - 10$	$9.80E - 08$	153
S_2	1	$1.86E - 08$	$1.00E - 09$	$2.53E - 08$	127
	2	$2.28E - 09$	$1.00E - 10$	$6.75E - 08$	253
	3	$1.47E - 09$	$1.00E - 10$	$9.29E - 08$	173

It is a key indicator of irreversibility within a system and its surroundings, reflecting the degree of disorder. Entropy generation arises when heat transfer within the system is incomplete or inefficient. The entropy generation equation can be expressed as follows (see Khan et al. [50]):

$$E_g = \underbrace{\frac{\kappa_f \kappa_{hnf}}{T_\infty^2 \kappa_f} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y}\right)^2}_{N_{HTI}} + \underbrace{\frac{\mu_{hnf}}{T_\infty} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^3 \right]}_{N_{VDI}} + \underbrace{\frac{\sigma_{hnf} B_0^2 u^2}{T_\infty}}_{N_{JDI}}, \quad (18)$$

The entropy generation E_g (see Eq. (8)) consists of three components representing different sources of irreversibility. The first term corresponds to entropy generation due to heat transfer (NHTI), the second term accounts for viscous dissipation effects (NFDI), and the third term represents irreversibility caused by Joule heating (NJDI). The dimensionless entropy generation number, denoted by N_s , is defined as:

$$N_s = Re_l \left[\frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \right] (\theta')^2 + Re_l \frac{Br}{\alpha_1} \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} \left[(F'')^2 + \frac{We}{\sqrt{2}} (F'')^3 \right] + Re_l \frac{Br}{\alpha_1} \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_f} M (F')^2. \quad (19)$$

where $Re_l = \frac{cl}{\nu_f}$, $Br = \frac{\mu_f u_w^2}{\kappa_f (T_w - T_\infty)} = Pr.Ec$, $\alpha_1 = \frac{T_w - T_\infty}{T_\infty}$.

3 Numerical solution procedure

The numerical resolution of the system described by Eqs. (12)–(13) with boundary conditions (14)–(15) was performed using the `bvp4c` solver in MATLAB. This solver employs a finite difference scheme based on the three-stage Lobatto IIIA implicit Runge-Kutta method. To achieve the desired accuracy, the solution is refined by adjusting the step size after providing an initial guess on the computational mesh. Shampine et al. [51] thoroughly discussed this approach, highlighting the critical role of appropriate initial guesses for successful convergence of the solver. It was observed that relatively simple initial guesses are sufficient to obtain the upper branch solutions, which satisfy the boundary conditions given in Eqs. (14)–(15) and correspond to velocity and temperature profiles with thinner boundary layers. Conversely, the lower branch solutions, which also comply with the boundary conditions but exhibit thicker boundary layers, demand more intricate initial guesses, making their computation more challenging and time-consuming. The following steps were undertaken to implement the `bvp4c` solver for the physical model: **Phase 1:** Introduce new variables as defined in Eq. (20) to convert the original nonlinear higher-order ODE system from Eqs. (12) and (13) into a first-order system suitable for numerical treatment.

$$y(1) = f, \quad y(2) = f', \quad y(3) = f'', \quad y(4) = \theta, \quad y(5) = \theta', \quad (20)$$

Phase 2: This conversion was crucial, setting a finite value of $\eta_\infty = 18$ and maintaining a constant relative tolerance of 1×10^{-6} across the problem-solving phase.

Let, $B_1 = \frac{(\rho_{hnf})}{\rho_f} / \left(\frac{\mu_f}{\mu_{hnf}} \right)$, $B_2 = \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_f}$, $B_3 = \frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f}$, $B_4 = \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f}$, $B_5 = \frac{\rho_{hnf}}{\rho_f}$ Equation (19), defining the new variables, transforms the higher-order nonlinear ODEs into an equivalent system of first-order nonlinear ODEs as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} f' = y'(1) \\ f'' = y'(2) \\ f''' = y'(3) \\ \theta' = y'(4) \\ \theta'' = y'(5) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} y(2) \\ y(3) \\ (B_1(-y(1)y(3) + y(2)y(2) + B_2 M y(2))) / (1 + B_1 Wey(3)) \\ y(5) \\ (Pr/B_4)(-B_3 y(1)y(5) - B_5(1 + 0.5Wey(3))Ecy(3)y(3)) \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Phase 3: The boundary conditions from Eqs. (13)–(14) are transformed to correspond with the new variables introduced in Eq. (20):

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_a(1) \\ y_a(2) \\ y_a(4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S \\ \lambda \\ 1 + (B_4/Bi)y(5) \end{pmatrix} \text{ at } \eta = 0, \quad \begin{pmatrix} y_b(2) \\ y_b(4) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (22)$$

Here, the subscript a denotes the location at the sheet's surface ($\eta = 0$), while b corresponds to the far-field boundary condition ($\eta = 18$). The existence of a second solution is influenced by the specific values of the governing parameters and the thickness of the boundary layer, demonstrating the sensitivity of the method to these conditions. **Phase 4:** Dual solutions were obtained by providing two different initial guesses sequentially to the `bvp4c` solver. The first solution can typically be found using relatively simple initial guesses; however, obtaining the second solution generally requires more carefully chosen, restrictive initial guesses. This process was repeated until the numerical solutions satisfactorily met the boundary conditions at infinity, as specified in Eq. (22).

4 Flow Stability

Since the boundary value problems described by Eqs. (12) and (13) can admit dual solutions (upper and lower branches), conducting a stability analysis becomes essential. This analysis determines whether the dual solutions of the boundary value problems given by Eqs. (7) and (8) are stable and physically relevant or unstable and thus impractical. For this purpose, the approach of Merkin [52] and Weidman et al. [53] is adopted. To carry out the stability analysis, the unsteady form of the problem is considered, leading to:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \sqrt{2}\Gamma \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2}, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}} \frac{d^2 T}{dy^2} + \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \Gamma \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^3 \right], \quad (24)$$

Following the approach of Wiani et al. [48], the temporal stability of the flow is analyzed by introducing the dimensionless time variable $\tau = at$. Applying this to Eq. (11), we obtain the transformed set of variables as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}} y, \quad \tau = at, \quad \psi = \sqrt{(c\nu_f)} x F(\eta, \tau), \quad u = cx F(\eta, \tau), \\ v &= -\sqrt{c\nu_f} F(\eta, \tau), \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where t is time and τ is the time variable. Substitute Eq. (25) into Eqs. (23) and (24) that are unsteady, the subsequent equations can be attained

$$\left(\frac{\mu_{hnf}/\mu_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f}\right)\frac{\partial^3 f}{\partial \eta^3} + We \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \eta^2} \frac{\partial^3 f}{\partial \eta^3} + F \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \eta^2} - \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta}\right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \eta \partial \tau} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{hnf}/\sigma_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f}\right) M F' = 0, \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \left(f \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta} - \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tau}\right) + \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} \left(1 + \frac{We}{2} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \eta^2}\right) Ec \left(\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \eta^2}\right)^2 = 0, \quad (27)$$

alongside the boundary conditions

$$f(\eta, \tau) = S, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta}(\eta, \tau) = \lambda, \quad \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \theta'(\eta, \tau) = -Bi(1 - \theta(\eta, \tau)), \quad \eta = 0, \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta}(\eta, \tau) \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) \rightarrow 0, \quad as \quad \eta \rightarrow \infty. \quad (29)$$

To determine the stability of the solutions, perturbation equations accounting for small disturbances must be applied, as outlined by Merkin [52] and Weidman et al. [53], to analyze Eqs. (26)–(29) and those are taken as:

$$f(\eta, \tau) = f_0(\eta) + e^{-\beta\tau} F(\eta), \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) = \theta_0(\eta) + e^{-\beta\tau} \Theta(\eta), \quad (30)$$

where where $f_0(\eta) = f(\eta)$, and $\theta_0(\eta) = \theta(\eta)$ by stability theory. Here, the functions $F(\eta, \tau)$ and $\Theta(\eta, \tau)$ are less than f_0 and θ_0 in case of steady flow solution and β is the unknown eigenvalue. By combining Eq. (30) into Eqs. (26)–(29) and setting τ to zero, it is possible to estimate the disturbance's initial decay or rise.

$$\frac{\mu_{hnf}/\mu_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f} F''' + We (F'' f_0''' + f_0'' F''') + (F f_0'' + f_0 F'') - 2f_0' F' + \beta F' - \frac{\sigma_{hnf}/\sigma_f}{\rho_{hnf}/\rho_f} M F' = 0, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \Theta'' + \frac{(\rho C_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} (f_0 \Theta' + F \theta_0') + \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f} \left(2\left(1 + \frac{We}{2} f_0''\right) Ec f_0'' F'' + \frac{We}{2} Ec F'' f_0''^2\right) = 0, \quad (32)$$

that conditioned to linearized boundary conditions

$$F(0) = S, \quad F'(0) = 0, \quad \frac{\kappa_{hnf}}{\kappa_f} \Theta'(0) = Bi \Theta(0), \quad (33)$$

$$F'(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \quad \Theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0. \quad (34)$$

By fixing the value of λ , the classical solution (f_0, θ_0) to the boundary value problems (12) and (13) is obtained. Following the approach of Harris et al. [54], who studied flow past a vertical flat plate using a second-order velocity model, the boundary condition $F_0'(\eta) \rightarrow 1$ as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ is replaced with the normalized

condition $F_0''(0) = 1$ to facilitate the solution of these problems. The stability analysis of the system was conducted using the bvp4c solver. When multiple solutions exist, the physically relevant solution is identified by selecting the one associated with the smallest eigenvalue β_1 , ordered as $\beta_1 < \beta_2 < \dots < \beta_n$. In this context, solutions with $\beta > 0$ correspond to physically stable states, while those with $\beta < 0$ are deemed unstable and nonphysical

Table 7

Skin-friction coefficients with Nusselt numbers (up to five decimal places)for fixed values of $\lambda = -1.0$, $S = 3.0$, $\phi_1 = 0.05$, $\phi_2 = 0.05$, $We = 0.2$, $M = 0.05$, $Ec = 0.05$ and $Pr = 6.8$.

<i>No of grids</i>	$Re_x^{1/2}C_f$	$Re_x^{1/2}C_f$	$Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$	$Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$
15	4.86102	0.15138	0.46919	0.48337
20	4.86102	0.15140	0.46919	0.48337
50	4.86102	0.15140	0.46919	0.48337
100	4.86102	0.15140	0.46919	0.48337
200	4.86102	0.15140	0.46919	0.48337
500	4.86102	0.15140	0.46919	0.48337

5 Grid independency test and numerical model validation

To verify the accuracy of the theoretical model coupled with the numerical method, a grid independence test was performed by varying the number of grid points. The test was conducted for parameters: $Pr = 6.8$, $S = 3.0$, $\lambda = -1.0$, $\phi_1 = 0.05$, $\phi_2 = 0.05$, $We = 0.1$, $Ec = 0.05$, and $M = 0.05$. Table 7 presents a sensitivity analysis of the numerical results for skin friction, and heat transfer rate, across different grid resolutions. It was observed that the solution accuracy improves significantly as the number of grid points increases. The variations in skin friction, and heat transferr between 15 and 500 grid points were carefully examined. The results indicate that the computed values stabilize and become independent of the grid size when the domain is discretized with 20 grid points. Consequently, a grid size of 100 points is adopted for all subsequent computations.

Table 8

Minimum eigenvalue β_1 for different combinations of S , λ , $\phi_{hmf}(= \phi_1 + \phi_2)$, We with $Pr = 6.8$, $M = 0.01$, $Ec = 0.01$, and $Bi = 0.1$.

β_1					
S	λ	ϕ_{hmf}	We	1st Solution	2nd Solution
4	-1.8	0.02	0.1	2.964706855	-1.552420364
3.8	-1.8	0.02	0.1	2.566822586	-1.458223724
3.8	-1.8	0.02	0.1	2.566822586	-1.458223724
3.5	-1.8	0.02	0.1	2.166275596	-1.306671145
3.2	-1.8	0.02	0.1	1.592207191	-1.103037965
3	-1.8	0.02	0.1	1.193046696	-0.906004893
2.8	-1.8	0.02	0.1	0.690161411	-0.586464012
2.7	-1.8	0.02	0.1	0.256327859	-0.240792508
3.5	-2	0.02	0.1	1.995887031	-1.320059077
3.5	-2.1	0.02	0.1	1.903072646	-1.310507307
3.5	-2.2	0.02	0.1	1.802399657	-1.287975698
3.5	-2.3	0.02	0.1	1.690048668	-1.250244127
3.5	-2.4	0.02	0.1	1.560650612	-1.19418932
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.1	1.407732011	-1.115072438
3.5	-2.6	0.02	0.1	1.222664321	-1.004927386
3.5	-2.7	0.02	0.1	0.989632665	-0.848001896
3.5	-2.8	0.02	0.1	0.665651542	-0.601216664
3.5	-2.85	0.02	0.1	0.415199681	-0.389736287
3.5	-2.5	0.2	0.1	2.096490857	-1.493950271
3.5	-2.5	0.18	0.1	2.117501005	-1.50410775
3.5	-2.5	0.16	0.1	2.119782077	-1.505205337
3.5	-2.5	0.14	0.1	2.101958262	-1.496599912
3.5	-2.5	0.12	0.1	2.062296554	-1.477246292
3.5	-2.5	0.1	0.1	1.998543958	-1.445537514
3.5	-2.5	0.08	0.1	1.907589952	-1.399003951
3.5	-2.5	0.06	0.1	1.784796236	-1.333731881
3.5	-2.5	0.04	0.1	1.622649404	-1.243146471
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.1	1.407732011	-1.115072438
3.5	-2.5	0.01	0.1	1.272792682	-1.029753237
3.5	-2.5	0.001	0.1	191.129179615	-0.934565212
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.01	1.75921596	-1.305472949
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.05	1.602683028	-1.226799118
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.1	1.407732011	-1.115072438
3.5	-2.5	0.02	0.2	0.97675659	-0.829475066

6 Results and discussion

The governing equations considered in this study consist of the Navier-Stokes equations, including continuity and momentum, along with the energy equation. The nonlinear nature of these equations is primarily responsible for the emergence of dual or multiple solutions. Such nonlinearities often cause bifurcations, particularly when variations in geometric or fluid dynamic parameters occur. Furthermore, the transition from laminar to turbulent flow involves a sequence of bifurcations, which complicates the solution landscape. Consequently, even under steady initial conditions, the system can exhibit unsteady behavior, allowing multiple valid solutions. The transformed ordinary differential equations (Eqs. (12) and (13)), subject to boundary conditions in Eqs. (14) and (15), were solved numerically using MATLAB's `bvp4c` solver. The resulting solution profiles are presented in Figures 2 to 14. To verify the accuracy and consistency of the present method, a comparison of the values $f''(0)$ and $-\theta'(0)$ has been conducted against the results obtained by Ghosh & Mukhopadhyay [47] and Waini et al. [48] for the case when $\lambda = -1$, $S = 3$, and $Pr = 0.7$, with all other parameters omitted. As shown in Table 4, the results exhibit excellent agreement, confirming the reliability of the current approach.

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the effects of the fluid flow on the skin friction coefficient, $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$, and the Nusselt number, $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$, for the *MgO-Ag*-water hybrid nanofluid. Notably, the behavior of Newtonian fluids differs markedly from that of non-Newtonian fluids. For the Williamson hybrid nanofluid, a considerable amount of mass suction is required to secure a solution. This research identifies two distinct regimes regarding similarity solutions: one where dual solutions exist and another where no solution can be found, both dependent on the mass suction parameter. These figures display the non-unique solutions of Eqs. (12) and (13) for various parameter sets, including suction parameters S ranging from 2.5 to 3.5, volume fractions $\phi_1 = 0.01$, $\phi_2 = 0.01$, Prandtl number $Pr = 6.8$, Weissenberg number $We = 0.1$, magnetic parameter $M = 0.1$, Eckert number $Ec = 0.1$, and Biot number $Bi = 0.5$, plotted against the shrinking parameter λ . It is important to note the critical values of λ : $\lambda_{c1} = -1.6611$, $\lambda_{c2} = -2.2780$, and $\lambda_{c3} = -2.9548$ for $S = 2.5$, 3.0, and 3.5 respectively. Increasing S leads to a decrease in the magnitude of $|\lambda_c|$, indicating that a stronger suction effect promotes earlier boundary layer separation. These figures reveal that dual solutions exist when the shrinking parameter $\lambda < 0$, specifically lies within the interval $\lambda_c < \lambda < -1$. Conversely, for $\lambda < \lambda_{ci} < 0$ (where $i = 1, 2, 3$), the boundary layer detaches from the sheet surface, resulting in the absence of solutions to the boundary value problem. Here, the critical values λ_{ci} correspond to points at which the problem admits real solutions and mark the transition between the first and second solution branches. Stability analysis confirms that only the first solution branch is physically meaningful and stable, while the second is not applicable in practi-

cal scenarios. Figure 2 demonstrates that the skin friction coefficient increases with higher suction values for the first solution branch, whereas the opposite trend is observed for the second branch. In contrast, Figure 3 shows an inverse relationship for the Nusselt number as suction intensifies. Physically, the suction S arrests the nanofluid motion by pulling fluid particles towards the sheet's surface, causing adherence and reducing velocity near the wall. Consequently, an inverse correlation exists between the nanofluid velocity and shear stress, leading to an increase in skin friction. This phenomenon is further accentuated by the shrinking sheet effect, which compresses the fluid, displacing it and thus causing velocity reduction and an increase in shear stress at the surface. Figure 3 further reveals that the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$ decreases as the suction parameter S increases, specifically in the context of the first solution branch. The Nusselt number, being a dimensionless measure of the ratio between convective and conductive heat transfer, implies that a reduction in its value corresponds to a decline in convective heat transfer relative to conduction. This phenomenon likely arises from the lower fluid velocity and elevated resistance to flow, both of which suppress the convective heat transport. The presence of wall suction results in a decreased temperature gradient $-\theta'(0)$ on the shrinking surface, thus reducing the surface heat transfer rate as indicated by the Nusselt number. In contrast, the second solution branch exhibits an opposite trend. These thermophysical behaviors are of significant relevance to engineering applications where effective heat transfer is essential, such as in heat exchangers, thermal regulation devices, and cooling systems. Figures 4 and 5 investigate the influence of the Weissenberg number (We) on the velocity and temperature profiles of the $MgO-Ag$ /water hybrid nanofluid, respectively. The parameter We quantifies the elastic behavior of the fluid; thus, higher values represent stronger viscoelastic effects. In viscoelastic fluids, such resistance opposes deformation due to shear stress, leading to a suppressed velocity profile in the first solution branch, as shown in Figure 4. However, the second branch demonstrates a contrasting response. This outcome underlines the significant impact of fluid elasticity on the nanofluid's flow dynamics. As illustrated in Figure 5, the temperature distribution increases with rising We values. This trend may be due to the viscoelastic resistance converting some of the fluid's mechanical energy into thermal energy through internal dissipation. This conversion enhances the thermal field in the dual solution region, indicating that elasticity contributes positively to the heat accumulation within the fluid system.

Figures 6 and 7 display the influence of the magnetic parameter M on the velocity and temperature profiles of the $MgO-Ag$ /water hybrid nanofluid. The magnetic parameter characterizes the intensity of the applied magnetic field in comparison to the fluid motion. When a magnetic field is applied, it generates electric currents within the electrically conducting hybrid nanofluid, producing a Lorentz force that acts against the motion of the fluid. This resistive force alters both the velocity distribution and the heat transfer characteristics of the flow. Concurrently, the shrinking nature of the surface tends to enhance

fluid velocity due to the converging motion, which pushes the surrounding fluid outward. The combined effects result in a slight increase in velocity and a reduction in temperature for the first solution branch. Conversely, the second solution branch shows an opposite response to the magnetic parameter, indicating reduced velocity and increased temperature under magnetic influence. Figure 8 illustrates how the Eckert number Ec affects the temperature distribution of the hybrid nanofluid. In both solution branches, higher values of Ec lead to elevated temperatures. This is because a larger Eckert number signifies more pronounced viscous dissipation, where kinetic energy is transformed into internal energy, thereby thickening the thermal boundary layer and elevating the temperature profile. Figure 9 illustrates how the thermal Biot number (Bi) influences the temperature distribution within the Williamson hybrid nanofluid. The findings show that as Bi increases, the temperature rises for both the stable and unstable solution branches. The Biot number quantifies the balance between convective and conductive heat transfer, with higher values indicating stronger convective dominance. As a result, more heat is transferred from the fluid to its surroundings, which elevates the overall temperature—especially near the shrinking surface where convection plays a more significant role.

Thermodynamic performance can be evaluated and improved using entropy generation or second law analysis, especially for nanofluids such as water-based $MgO-Ag$. Figures 10 and 11 demonstrate how the volume fractions of nanoparticles ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and the Weissenberg number (We) influence entropy generation. As depicted, increasing either the nanoparticle concentrations or the elasticity parameter We leads to a rise in entropy generation in both stable and unstable solution branches. This enhancement is more pronounced near the sheet's surface and diminishes with increasing distance from the wall (i.e., increasing η), indicating that entropy generation is highly sensitive to these parameters in the near-wall region. These findings are consistent with established physical principles and align with prior research. The results suggest that optimizing these parameters can enhance second-law performance and overall system efficiency.

Figures 12 and 13 illustrate the effects of the Weissenberg number We and the material characteristics—specifically, the total volume fraction of nanoparticles $\phi_{hnf}(= \phi_1 (MgO) + \phi_2 (Ag))$ —on the skin friction coefficient $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$ and the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$. Three distinct fluid types are considered in this comparison: regular fluid (RF) with $\phi_{hnf} = 0$ ($\phi_1 = 0.0$, $\phi_2 = 0.0$), nanofluid (NF) consisting of MgO /water with $\phi_{hnf} = 0.01$ ($\phi_1 = 0.01$, $\phi_2 = 0.0$), and hybrid nanofluid (HNF) made up of $MgO-Ag$ /water with $\phi_{hnf} = 0.02$ ($\phi_1 = 0.01$, $\phi_2 = 0.01$). For the first (physically stable) solution branch, the $MgO-Ag$ /water hybrid nanofluid (HNF) exhibits the highest skin friction among the three fluids, as seen in Figs. 12(a-b). This increase in $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$ results from enhanced viscous forces due to greater nanoparticle loading. However, in the second (unstable) solution branch, the trend reverses—skin friction decreases with increasing nanoparticle volume fraction.

As the total nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{hnf} increases, fluid velocity is suppressed due to increased resistance, thus enhancing wall shear stress and increasing skin friction in the stable case. The behavior of the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$, a dimensionless parameter representing the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer, is illustrated in Figs. 12(c-d). An increase in ϕ_{hnf} leads to a decline in $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$, indicating that thermal conduction becomes more dominant relative to convection. This decline is attributed to the thickening of the thermal boundary layer and a reduction in convective transport caused by higher nanoparticle concentrations. Among all cases, the hybrid nanofluid (HNF) demonstrates the lowest Nusselt number in both solution branches. Furthermore, the influence of the Weissenberg number We (Newtonian ($We = 0.0$) and non-Newtonian ($We = 0.1$)) is also notable in Figs. 12(a-d). For the first solution branch, an increase in We enhances both the skin friction coefficient and the Nusselt number, suggesting stronger elastic effects and improved heat transfer performance. In contrast, the second solution exhibits the opposite behavior: higher We reduces both $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$ and $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$. These results highlight the critical role of fluid elasticity and nanoparticle volume fraction in modifying flow and thermal characteristics in non-Newtonian hybrid nanofluid systems. Figures 13(a-b) demonstrate that as the volume fraction of nanoparticles increases, the skin friction coefficient $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$ for hybrid nanofluid also rises. This enhancement is attributed to the greater density and thermal conductivity of the hybrid nanofluid, which facilitate improved momentum transfer and lead to increased flow resistance. When the combined nanoparticle concentration is varied from 0% to 5%, particle-particle and particle-fluid interactions intensify. These interactions introduce additional obstructions within the fluid, disrupting flow patterns and thereby decreasing the overall fluid velocity. Furthermore, the hydrodynamic interaction causes the fluid to be dragged along in the direction of nanoparticle motion, enhancing the shear stress on the boundary. Consequently, increasing the volume fractions of MgO and Ag in the hybrid nanofluid leads to a rise in $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$, as observed in both the first (stable) and second (unstable) solution branches. Additionally, the behavior of Newtonian ($We = 0.0$) and non-Newtonian ($We = 0.1$) fluids is compared. For the first solution branch, non-Newtonian fluids exhibit greater skin friction due to the viscoelastic properties imparted by the Weissenberg number. This can be explained by the increase in fluid–surface interactions caused by fluid elasticity, which raises friction at the interface. However, in the second solution branch, the trend is reversed—Newtonian fluids show higher skin friction than their non-Newtonian counterparts. Figures 13(c-d) focus on the Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$ and its variation with total nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{hnf} . It is observed that increasing ϕ_{hnf} reduces the Nusselt number in both solution branches. This inverse relationship occurs because higher solid concentrations expand the thermal boundary layer and hinder convective transport. A comparative analysis between Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids reveals that the presence of viscoelastic effects (non-zero We) slightly enhances the heat transfer capability, likely due

to greater internal resistance and increased energy dissipation, which raises the fluid temperature. Consequently, the Nusselt number increases with We . These findings support the concept that the synergistic combination of multiple nanoparticles in hybrid nanofluids can enhance thermal conductivity, alter velocity gradients, and modify flow behavior. Such properties make hybrid nanofluids valuable in industrial applications requiring enhanced heat transfer efficiency—such as high-performance heat exchangers, advanced cooling technologies, and thermal management in miniaturized systems—where accurate modeling of thermal processes is essential.

In the present investigation, a stability analysis is essential due to the existence of dual (multiple) solutions. To conduct this analysis, the boundary value problem defined by Eqs. (31) and (33), together with the associated boundary conditions (33)–(34), was numerically solved using the `bvp4c` solver available in MATLAB. This method facilitated the computation of the smallest eigenvalues, represented by β_1 , which are crucial in assessing the temporal stability of the obtained solutions. The stability behavior hinges on the sign of β_1 . Specifically, when $\beta_1 > 0$, the term $e^{-\beta_1\tau}$ tends to zero as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, indicating the decay of perturbations and implying that the solution is stable over time. Conversely, if $\beta_1 < 0$, the term $e^{-\beta_1\tau}$ diverges as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, suggesting that disturbances grow with time, and hence, the solution becomes unstable. Based on this criterion, it is concluded that the first solution branch corresponds to a physically realizable and stable flow configuration, while the second branch is unstable and not physically sustainable in the long term. A negative value of β_1 signifies the initial amplification of perturbations, leading to an unstable flow configuration, whereas a positive β_1 denotes the initial attenuation of disturbances, implying flow stability. To investigate the influence of various governing parameters on the stability characteristics, we evaluated the eigenvalue β_1 for several combinations of S , λ , ϕ_{hnf} , and We , keeping other parameters fixed as $Pr = 6.8$, $M = 0.01$, $Ec = 0.01$, and $Bi = 0.1$. The computed results, displayed in Table 8, reveal that the first solution is associated with positive values of β_1 , indicating a stable regime, while the second solution consistently corresponds to negative β_1 values, signifying an unstable flow regime. These outcomes are in good agreement with previous studies and further substantiate the dual nature of solutions in such flow scenarios. An interesting observation is that the smallest eigenvalue β_1 for both solution branches approaches zero as the suction parameter S decreases, suggesting convergence toward a critical point. A similar trend is evident with increasingly negative values of the shrinking parameter λ , where both branches exhibit minimal β_1 values nearing zero. This convergence behavior is also observed when the nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{hnf} and the Weissenberg number We are enhanced. These results emphasize the sensitive dependence of solution stability on flow control parameters and hybrid nanofluid composition. Figure 14 illustrates the behavior of the smallest eigenvalue β_1 in response to variations in the shrinking parameter λ for the *MgO-Ag*/water hybrid nanofluid (HNF) flow over a shrinking sheet. The top portion of the figure corresponds to the domain of stable so-

lutions, whereas the bottom half indicates regions of instability. Notably, the critical values of the shrinking parameter λ are identified at $\lambda_c = -2.8825$ for $S = 3.5$ and $\lambda_c = -2.202$ for $S = 3.0$. At these points, the curves representing the smallest eigenvalues for both the stable and unstable branches intersect, signifying a transition point or bifurcation where the nature of the solution stability changes.

7 Predicating flow and heat transfer using ANN

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computational models inspired by the neural structure of the human brain, designed to process complex and large-scale datasets that challenge conventional statistical approaches. The fundamental unit in an ANN is the artificial neuron, which facilitates the identification of underlying patterns between input and output variables. Due to this capability, ANNs are widely employed for tasks such as data classification, clustering, and prediction. Typically, an ANN architecture includes three layers: input, hidden, and output layers, with the number of neurons in the hidden layer being adjustable to suit the problem complexity. The network's optimal configuration and connection weights are established through training with empirical data and validation. Using back-propagation, the network iteratively updates weights to minimize the error between predicted and actual outcomes. Figure 15 depicts the structure of the proposed network, where 70% of the data is used for training, and 15% each are reserved for validation and testing. Training data helps the model learn by minimizing mean squared error (MSE), validation data prevents overfitting, and testing data assesses prediction accuracy.

The analyzed dataset, detailed in Table 5, consists of three cases under two scenarios and is generated through numerical solutions obtained by the `bvp4c` method in MATLAB for 10 parameters. To evaluate ANN stability, duplicate runs for scenarios S_1 and S_2 were performed. Scenario S_1 achieved better MSE with 290 epochs for Case 2, while S_2 reached similar accuracy with only 253 epochs, indicating faster convergence. The graphical results demonstrating ANN performance and accuracy for both scenarios in Case 2 are presented in Figures 16–20. Table 5 presents a detailed comparison of the efficiency, μ values, gradients, and epochs for the training, validation, and testing phases, offering a thorough analysis of both computational and randomized datasets. Figures 16(a) and 16(b) illustrate the mean squared error (MSE) progression for these phases in Case 3 across the two scenarios. The MSE decreases steadily, reaching values between 10^{-7} and 10^{-9} at 393 and 611 epochs respectively, indicating excellent reliability and precision. The plots show that the MSE starts at relatively high values and gradually diminishes throughout training, with the lowest MSE observed at 8.296×10^{-7} at the 290th epoch for

scenario S_1 , and 9.216×10^{-9} at the 253rd epoch for S_2 , as depicted in Fig. 16. The convergence of training, validation, and testing error curves towards an ideal baseline suggests optimal completion of the ANN training. Furthermore, Figures 17(a) and 17(b) provide precise values for the gradient, μ , and validation checks obtained during the training stages, which serve as step-size parameters in the replication for Case 2 under both scenarios. Here, " μ " represents the damping parameter in the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, which regulates the learning rate to ensure stable and efficient convergence. At epochs 290 and 253, slope values of 9.642×10^{-8} and 6.746×10^{-8} with μ values of 1×10^{-11} for both S_1 and S_2 respectively were recorded. The accuracy and consistency of the training trends for each dataset are further evaluated using error histograms shown in Figures 18(a) and 18(b), where the error distributions are centered around zero, indicating minimal bias. Correlation analysis, as displayed in Figures 19(a) and 19(b), assesses the relationship between input parameters and network predictions, with correlation coefficients (R) equal to 1 for training, validation, and testing phases, signifying an ideal fit. The scatter plots confirm that predicted outputs align closely with expected values, demonstrating the model's high predictive capability and highlighting areas with minimal deviations. Finally, Figure 20(a) and 20(b) compare the ANN outcomes with benchmark numerical results obtained via the `bvp4c` solver for hybrid nanofluid flow, considering input errors in the range of 1 to 2 with a step size of 0.001. This comparison validates the neural network's accuracy and effectiveness in modeling the problem under investigation.

8 Conclusion

This study explores the stability of dual solutions in the non-Newtonian Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow subjected to a transverse magnetic field over a shrinking sheet. The investigation integrates a computational technique based on MATLAB's `bvp4c` solver with a data-driven approach using artificial neural networks (ANN). A single-hidden-layer ANN model is trained using the Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation method, leveraging benchmark solutions generated from the numerical scheme. The physical model incorporates the effects of viscous dissipation and convective thermal boundary conditions. The hybrid nanofluid is composed of Magnesium Oxide (MgO) and Silver (Ag) nanoparticles suspended in water as the base fluid. Such fluid dynamics are highly relevant in engineering applications including electronic cooling, heat exchanger systems, and advanced thermal regulation processes. To simplify the governing partial differential equations, similarity transformations are used to reduce the model to a system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs), which are then solved using the `bvp4c` method. The performance of

the ANN in approximating the physical behavior is assessed through error histograms, regression plots, mean squared error metrics, and convergence behavior. Results are analyzed in terms of velocity distributions, temperature fields, skin friction coefficients, and Nusselt numbers. From the conducted analyses, several critical insights were obtained:

- (1) Dual solutions are observed only for flows over a shrinking surface. These dual branches exist within a defined interval of the shrinking parameter λ , specifically when $\lambda \geq \lambda_{c1}$, λ_{c2} , and λ_{c3} for various values of the suction parameter S .
- (2) A linear stability analysis, based on the smallest eigenvalue β_1 , confirms that the first solution branch is stable, while the second branch is unstable. Positive eigenvalues indicate decay of perturbations over time, validating stability.
- (3) The velocity profile of the Williamson hybrid nanofluid shows a decreasing trend with an increase in the Weissenberg number We due to enhanced fluid elasticity. Conversely, it improves with the magnetic parameter M owing to the Lorentz force effects in the stable solution regime.
- (4) Temperature profiles rise with increasing Weissenberg number We and Eckert number Ec , reflecting enhanced viscous dissipation and elastic resistance. However, the temperature decreases with a stronger magnetic field in the stable branch.
- (5) Skin friction coefficient $Re_x^{1/2}C_f$ increases with both the nanoparticle volume fraction and higher values of We . This enhancement is more significant in hybrid nanofluids compared to conventional nanofluids or pure base fluids.
- (6) The Nusselt number $Re_x^{-1/2}Nu_x$, indicative of convective heat transfer, declines as the hybrid nanoparticle volume fraction increases. This reduction is more prominent in hybrid nanofluids than in nanofluids or regular fluids.
- (7) Entropy generation profiles increase with the nanoparticle volume fractions ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , as well as with the Weissenberg number We , indicating higher thermodynamic irreversibility near the surface.
- (8) The non-Newtonian behavior of the Williamson fluid significantly affects temperature distribution, skin friction, and heat transfer characteristics. The stability analysis confirms that only the first solution is practically relevant.
- (9) The artificial neural network (ANN) approach demonstrates high predictive accuracy. Regression and mean squared error (MSE) analyses yield values ranging from 10^{-7} to 10^{-9} , confirming the robustness of the numerical and data-driven solutions.

9 Data Availability

All data generated or analysed during this study are free available and also included in this article.

10 Declaration of Conflicting Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Devi, S.A. and Devi, S.S.U., 2016. Numerical investigation of hydromagnetic hybrid $Cu-Al_2O_3$ /water nanofluid flow over a permeable stretching sheet with suction. *International Journal of Nonlinear Sciences and Numerical Simulation*, 17(5), pp.249-257.
- [2] Sajjad, M., Mujtaba, A., Asghar, A. and Ying, T.Y., 2022. Dual solutions of magnetohydrodynamics $Al_2O_3 + Cu$ hybrid nanofluid over a vertical exponentially shrinking sheet by presences of joule heating and thermal slip condition. *CFD Lett*, 14(8), pp.100-115.
- [3] Devi, S.U. and Devi, S.A., 2017. Heat transfer enhancement of $Cu - Al_2O_3$ /water hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet. *Journal of the Nigerian Mathematical Society*, 36(2), pp.419-433.
- [4] Hayat, T. and Nadeem, S., 2017. Heat transfer enhancement with $Ag-CuO$ /water hybrid nanofluid. *Results in physics*, 7, pp.2317-2324.
- [5] Jamshed, W., Devi, S.U. and Nisar, K.S., 2021. Single phase based study of $Ag-Cu/EO$ Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching surface with shape factor. *Physica Scripta*, 96(6), p.065202.
- [6] Sreedevi, P., Sudarsana Reddy, P. and Chamkha, A., 2020. Heat and mass transfer analysis of unsteady hybrid nanofluid flow over a stretching sheet with thermal radiation. *SN Applied Sciences*, 2(7), p.1222.
- [7] Anuar, N.S., Bachok, N. and Pop, I., 2021. Influence of buoyancy force on $Ag-MgO$ /water hybrid nanofluid flow in an inclined permeable stretching/shrinking sheet. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 123, p.105236.
- [8] Dharmiah, G., Goud, B.S., Nisar, K.S. and Reddy, Y.D., 2025. A study of hybrid nano $Ag-MgO-H_2O$ flow fluid past a slim needle with thermal radiation and Neild's boundary. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, p.106328.
- [9] Soomro, A.M., Fadhel, M.A., Lund, L.A., Shah, Z., Alshehri, M.H. and Vrinceanu, N., 2024. Dual solutions of magnetized radiative flow of Cas-

- son Nanofluid over a stretching/shrinking cylinder: Stability analysis. *Helvion*, 10(8).
- [10] Revnic, C., Grosan, T. and Pop, I., 2025. Dual solutions of ternary hybrid nanofluids stagnation point over a linearly stretching/shrinking sheet. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, pp.1-10.
- [11] Ouyang, Y., Basir, M.F.M., Naganthran, K. and Pop, I., 2024. Dual solutions in Maxwell ternary nanofluid flow with viscous dissipation and velocity slip past a stretching/shrinking sheet. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 105, pp.437-448.
- [12] Williamson, R.V., 1929. The flow of pseudoplastic materials. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry*, 21(11), pp.1108-1111.
- [13] Kulkarni, M. and Shankar, H.F., 2024. Numerical investigation of mixed convective Williamson nanofluid flow over a stretching/shrinking wedge in the presence of chemical reaction parameter and liquid hydrogen diffusion. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, pp.1-14.
- [14] Abbas, M.S., Qamar, M., Khan, M. and Hussain, S.M., 2025. Chemically reactive flow of Williamson nanofluid with nonlinear thermal radiation over an exponentially stretching/shrinking surface. *Journal of Radiation Research and Applied Sciences*, 18(3), p.101630.
- [15] Rehman, A., Khun, M.C., Inc, M., Chou, D. and Rezapour, S., 2025. Analytical simulation for couple stress Williamson nanofluid flow and heat transfer towards a shrinking surface with slip and viscous dissipation effects. *ZAMM-Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics/Zeitschrift für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik*, 105(1), p.e202400890.
- [16] Saini, S.K., Agrawal, R. and Mandal, G., 2025. Stability analysis of dual solutions for unsteady MHD Darcy-Forchheimer Williamson nanofluid flow over a shrinking surface with chemical reaction and viscous dissipation. *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*, 8(8), p.347.
- [17] Gomathi, N. and Poulomi, D., 2024. Dual solutions of Casson Williamson nanofluid with thermal radiation and chemical reaction. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, pp.1-24.
- [18] Jamrus, F.N., Ishak, A., Waini, I., Khan, U., Hussain, S.M., Madhukesh, J.K. and Abed, A.M., 2025. Stability scrutinization of a non-Newtonian (Williamson) ternary hybrid nanofluid past a stretching/shrinking sheet. *ZAMM-Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics/Zeitschrift für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik*, 105(2), p.e202300926.
- [19] Mandal, G. and Pal, D., 2022. Entropy generation analysis of magnetohydrodynamic Darcy-Forchheimer Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow through porous medium with nonlinear thermal radiation. *Special Topics & Reviews in Porous Media: An International Journal*, 13(3).
- [20] Hartmann, J., 1937, Theory of the Laminar Flow of an Electrically Conductive Liquid in a Homogeneous Magnetic Field. *Fys. Med.*, 15, 1-27.
- [21] Bhatti, M.M., Arain, M.B., Zeeshan, A., Ellahi, R. and Doranehgard, M.H., 2022. Swimming of Gyrotactic Microorganism in MHD Williamson

- nanofluid flow between rotating circular plates embedded in porous medium: Application of thermal energy storage. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 45, p.103511.
- [22] Nasir, N.A.A.M., Zainuddin, N., Khashi'ie, N.S., Ishak, A. and Pop, I., 2022. Influence of Induced Magnetic Over Stagnation Point $Ag - MgO/H_2O$ Hybrid Nanofluid Flow and Heat Transfer Towards Moving Surface. In *Intelligent Systems Modeling and Simulation II: Machine Learning, Neural Networks, Efficient Numerical Algorithm and Statistical Methods* (pp. 447-465). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- [23] Alkasasbeh, H.T. and Mohamed, M.K.A., 2023. MHD (SWCNTS+MWCNTS)/ H_2O -based Williamson hybrid nanofluids flow past exponential shrinking sheet in porous medium. *Frontiers in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 21, pp.265-279.
- [24] Maiti, H. and Nandy, S.K., 2023. Scrutinization of unsteady magnetohydrodynamics Williamson nanofluid flow and heat transfer past a permeable shrinking sheet. *Journal of Nanofluids*, 12(4), pp.1095-1106.
- [25] Jakeer, S. and Reddy, P.B.A., 2024. Stability analysis of electrical magneto hydrodynamic stagnation point flow of $Ag - Cu$ /water hybrid nanofluid over a permeable stretching/shrinking slendering sheet: Entropy generation. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*, 238(3), pp.1172-1184.
- [26] Sakkaravarthi, K. and P, B.A.R., 2024. Entropy generation on MHD flow of Williamson hybrid nanofluid over a permeable curved stretching/shrinking sheet with various radiations. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals*, 85(3), pp.231-257.
- [27] Mandal, G. and Pal, D., 2024. Entropy generation minimization and activation energy in magneto-thermo-solutal stratified Ellis hybrid nanofluid flow through a stretching stenotic artery: Insights into cardiovascular disease. *Thermal Advances*, 1, p.100004.
- [28] Mandal, G. and Pal, D., 2025. Stability and multiple solutions of MHD-quadratic radiative tri-hybrid nanofluid flow in a Darcy–Forchheimer porous medium over a rotating shrinking disk. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*.
- [29] Talukdar, B. and Mandal, G., 2025. Magneto-Radiative Nanofluid Flow over a Stretching Permeable Sheet with Heat Generation and Slip Boundary Effects: Homotopy Perturbation Method. *Sustainable Chemical Engineering*, pp.114-129.
- [30] Roy, N.C. and Pop, I., 2023. Dual solutions of a nanofluid flow past a convectively heated nonlinearly shrinking sheet. *Chinese Journal of Physics*, 82, pp.31-40.
- [31] Khashi'ie, N.S., Roşca, N.C., Roşca, A.V. and Pop, I., 2023. Dual solutions on MHD radiative three-dimensional bidirectional nanofluid flow over a non-linearly permeable shrinking sheet. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 71, pp.401-411.
- [32] Abu Bakar, S., Pop, I. and Md Arifin, N., 2025. Dual solutions of hybrid

- nanofluid flow past a permeable melting shrinking sheet with higher-order slips, shape factor and viscous dissipation effect. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*, 35(1), pp.199-230.
- [33] Kaswan, P., Kumar, M., Kumari, M. and Mandal, G., 2024. Stability analysis of dual solutions for nonlinear radiative magnetohydrodynamic flow of $Ag - TiO_2/H_2O$ hybrid nanofluid over a nonlinearly shrinking surface. *Thermal Advances*, 1, p.100002.
- [34] Khan, Z., Khan, W., Arko, Y.A., Egami, R.H. and Garalleh, H.A., 2025. Numerical stability of magnetized Williamson nanofluid over a stretching/shrinking sheet with velocity and thermal slips effect. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part B: Fundamentals*, 86(6), pp.1763-1783.
- [35] Ziaei-Rad, M., Saeedan, M. and Afshari, E., 2016. Simulation and prediction of MHD dissipative nanofluid flow on a permeable stretching surface using artificial neural network. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 99, pp.373-382.
- [36] Ul-Haq, S., Tanveer, A., Ashraf, M.B. and Nawaz, R., 2025. Artificial neural network (ANN) analysis of non-similar solution of MHD nanofluid flow past a curved stretching surface. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, 86(8), pp.2399-2422.
- [37] Raja, M.A.Z., Latif, A., Shamim, M., Nisar, K.S. and Shoaib, M., 2025. Design of artificial neural network for buongiorno model with nanofluids flow through stretching sheet. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 69, p.106054.
- [38] Roy, N.C. and Pop, I., 2023. Dual solutions of a nanofluid flow past a convectively heated nonlinearly shrinking sheet. *Chinese Journal of Physics*, 82, pp.31-40.
- [39] Alimi, F., Rehman, S., Bouzidi, M., Asiri, F., Saidani, T. and Tirth, V., 2025. Numerical and artificial neural network framework for predicating MHD radiative flow and heat transfer of hybrid nanofluid with Cattaneo-Christov theory. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, p.106311.
- [40] Naveen, P., Tantry, M.M., Sathya, P. and Sindhuja, S., 2025. Artificial neural network modelling for Casson hybrid nanofluid flow with entropy generation analysis. *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*, 8(6), p.288.
- [41] Jabeen, K., Mushtaq, M., Mushtaq, T. and Muntazir, R.M.A., 2024. A numerical study of boundary layer flow of Williamson nanofluid in the presence of viscous dissipation, bioconvection, and activation energy. *Numerical Heat Transfer, Part A: Applications*, 85(3), pp.378-399.
- [42] Alhowaity, A., Hamam, H., Bilal, M. and Ali, A., 2022. Numerical study of Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with thermal characteristics past over an extending surface. *Heat transfer*, 51(7), pp.6641-6655.
- [43] Mumtaz, F., Abbas, T., Jhangeer, A. and Ali, I., 2024. Analysis of thermal significances of nanofluids in inclined magnetized flow with Joule heating source and slip effects. *Nano-Structures & Nano-Objects*, 40, p.101349.
- [44] Aly, E.H. and Pop, I., 2019. MHD flow and heat transfer over a perme-

- able stretching/shrinking sheet in a hybrid nanofluid with a convective boundary condition. *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat & Fluid Flow*, 29(9), pp.3012-3038.
- [45] Khashi'ie, N.S., Arifin, N.M., Pop, I. and Wahid, N.S., 2020. Flow and heat transfer of hybrid nanofluid over a permeable shrinking cylinder with Joule heating: A comparative analysis. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 59(3), pp.1787-1798.
- [46] Rashad, A.M., Nafe, M.A. and Eisa, D.A., 2023. Heat variation on MHD Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow with convective boundary condition and Ohmic heating in a porous material. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), p.6071.
- [47] Ghosh S. and Mukhopadhyay S. Stability analysis for model-based study of nanofluid flow over an exponentially shrinking permeable sheet in presence of slip, *Neural. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 7201– 7211, Jul 2020. DOI: 10.1007/s00521-019-04221-w.
- [48] Waini I., Ishak A. and Pop I. , Multiple solutions of the unsteady hybrid nanofluid flow over a rotating disk with stability analysis, *Eur. J. Mech. - B/Fluids*, vol. 94, pp. 121–127, Jul 2022. 2022.02.011. DOI: 10.1016/j.euromechflu.2022.02.011.
- [49] Mandal, G. and Pal, D., 2022. Entropy generation analysis of magneto-hydrodynamic Darcy-Forchheimer Williamson hybrid nanofluid flow through porous medium with nonlinear thermal radiation. *Special Topics & Reviews in Porous Media: An International Journal*, 13(3).
- [50] Khan, M.N., Ahmad, S., Wang, Z., Fadhil, B.M., Irshad, K., Eldin, S.M., Pasha, A.A., Al Mesfer, M.K. and Danish, M., 2023. Enhancement in the efficiency of heat recovery in a Williamson hybrid nanofluid over a vertically thin needle with entropy generation. *Heliyon*, 9(7).
- [51] Shampine, L.F., Gladwell, I. and Thompson, S., 2003. *Solving ODEs with matlab*. Cambridge university press.
- [52] Merkin, J.H., 1986. On dual solutions occurring in mixed convection in a porous medium. *Journal of engineering Mathematics*, 20(2), pp.171-179.
- [53] Weidman, P.D., Kubitschek, D.G. and Davis, A.M.J., 2006. The effect of transpiration on self-similar boundary layer flow over moving surfaces. *International journal of engineering science*, 44(11-12), pp.730-737.
- [54] Harris, S.D., Ingham, D.B. and Pop, I., 2009. Mixed convection boundary-layer flow near the stagnation point on a vertical surface in a porous medium: Brinkman model with slip. *Transport in Porous Media*, 77(2), pp.267-285.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the problem.

Fig. 2. Skin-friction curve against shrinking parameter λ for different suction parameter S .

Fig. 3. Nusselt number curve against shrinking parameter λ for different suction parameter S .

Fig. 4. Velocity curves for different Weissenberg number We .

Fig. 5. Temperature curves for different Weissenberg number We .

Fig. 6. Velocity curves for for different magnetic parameter M .

Fig. 7. Temperature curves for for different magnetic parameter M .

Fig. 8. Temperature curves for different Eckert number Ec .

Fig. 9. Temperature curves for different Biot number Bi .

Fig. 10. Entropy generation curves for different volume fraction parameters ϕ_1, ϕ_2 .

Fig. 11. Entropy generation curves for different Weissenberg number We .

Fig 21(a)

Fig 21(b)

Fig 21(c)

Fig 21(d)

Fig. 12. Skin friction performance (a)-(b) and Nusselt number variation (c)-(d) for different type of fluids and Weissenberg number We .

22(a)

22(b)

22(c)

22(d)

Fig. 13. Skin friction performance (a)-(b) and Nusselt number variation (c)-(d) for different nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_{hnf} and Weissenberg number We .

Fig. 14. Variation of smallest eigenvalue β_1 against λ .

Fig. 15. Structural design of ANN.

Fig. 16. ANN presentation for testing, performance, validation of case 2: (a) for S_1 and (b) for S_2 .

Fig. 17. Evaluation of ANN for gradient, Mu and validation of case 2: (a) for S_1 and (b) for S_2 .

Fig. 18. Error scattering via Histogram of case 2: (a) for S_1 and (b) for S_2 .

Fig. 19. Regression analysis of case 2: (a) for S_1 and (b) for S_2 .

Fig. 20. Comparison of referee solution through ANN of case 2: (a) for S_1 and (b) for S_2 .